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Research Article

**RP-HPLC TECHNIQUE FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION
OF REMOGLIFLOZIN AND METFORMIN IN BULK AND
FORMULATION**B.Gayathri¹, P.Aravindra Reddy²¹Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy, N.F.C Nagar, Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.

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Abstract:

The most common and powerful approach for drug analysis is high-performance liquid chromatography. The current study focuses on the development and validation of innovative RP-HPLC analytical techniques for the development of drug contents in solid oral dosage forms. In the therapeutic drug monitoring and pharmaceutical sectors, method development is critical. It is always preferable to choose and develop a method for determining pharmaceuticals in pharmaceutical dosage forms and biological fluid samples that is straightforward, accurate, exact, and cost-effective. In the discovery, development, and production of drugs and pharmaceuticals, analytical method development and validation are critical. The new simple, novel, precise, rapid, reliable, accurate, and reproducible reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) technique for simultaneous estimation of Remogliflozin and Metformin in bulk and formulation. The separation was achieved using ODS, C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, i.d.2.5 μm) column with isocratic elution. A mixture of acetonitrile: 20 mM ammonium formate buffer (pH 3.5) at the ratio of (60:40) as a mobile phase with a flow rate of 1.0 ml min⁻¹ was used for the separation of analytes. The separated effluents were monitored with a diode array detector at 243 nm. The results showed good linearity over a range of 2.5–25 μg ml⁻¹ and 12.5–125 μg ml⁻¹ for Remogliflozin and Metformin respectively. Furthermore, the average percentage assay of marketed formulations of Remogliflozin and Metformin was found to be 100.30% and 100.52 %, respectively. Remogliflozin limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) were 0.42 and 1.28 μg ml⁻¹ while LOD and LOQ for Metformin were 1.97 and 5.96 μg ml⁻¹ respectively.

Keywords: Remogliflozin, Metformin, Simultaneous estimation, Method development, ICH, RP-HPLC.**Corresponding author:****P.Aravindra Reddy,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Remogliflozin Etabonate IUPAC name Ethyl[(2R,3S,4S,5R,6S)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-[5-methyl-1-propan-2-yl-4-[(4-propan-2-yloxyphenyl)methyl]pyrazol[3-yl]oxyoxan-2-yl]methyl carbonate. It is soluble in methanol. It is an oral hypoglycemic agent; it is used for type 2 diabetes. It is Inhibitor of sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) it is expressed in the proximal renal tubules and is responsible for the majority of the reabsorption of filtered glucose from the tubular lumen by inhibiting SGLT2, it also reduces reabsorption of filtered glucose and lowers the renal threshold for glucose and thereby increases urinary glucose excretion.

Metformin Hydrochloride IUPAC name 3-(diaminomethylidene)-1,1-dimethylguanidine; hydrochloride. It is Freely Soluble in water, methanol. It is used for the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It's an antihyperglycemic medication that improves glucose tolerance in type 2 diabetic patients by reducing both basal and postprandial plasma glucose levels. Metformin improves insulin sensitivity by boosting peripheral glucose uptake and utilization. It lowers hepatic glucose production, lowers intestinal glucose absorption, and lowers hepatic glucose production.

Literature review reveals that few methods are reported for determination of Remogliflozin etabonate and metformin hcl by UV spectroscopy,[03] LC-MS/MS.[04] The aim of the present work was to develop stability indicating RP-HPLC Method for the Estimation of Remogliflozin Etabonate and metformin hcl in its dosage forms. Because analytical methods must be validated before use by the pharmaceutical industry, the proposed RP-HPLC detection method was validated in accordance with International conference in Harmonization (ICH)[05] guidelines, by assessing its selectivity, linearity, accuracy, and precision, limit of detection and limit of quantification in this method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS Chemicals and Reagents Remogliflozin Etabonate and metformin hcl were procured ,HPLC grade reagents methanol, acetonitrile were used for study. The entire reagent prepared by carbon dioxide free water and whereas the sample solution prepared in double Distilled water for HPLC Purpose.

Apparatus:

RP-HPLC method development and validation was done on a HPLC instrument (LC- 10AT, 20 μ L fixed loop. Spinchrom) UV Detector, Stationary Phase used was Cosmosil C18 (25cm $\times$ 0.46cm), 5 μ m

column particle size and mobile phase consisting of Buffer, (phosphate Buffer (pH 4.2): Acetonitrile (60:40) was used. The flow rate was 1.0 ml/min and the effluents were monitored at 241nm. Injection volume was 20 μ L. All weighing were done on analytical balance(Shimadzu).

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

The mobile phase used in this study was composed of acetonitrile: ammonium formate buffer (pH 3.5) at the ratio of 40:60 % v/v, with isocratic elution. Filtration was done by 0.45-micron nylon membrane (Millipore) filter and an ultrasonic bath was used to degassed before further use to circumvent conflicts and clogging of the column due to small particles. Standard & sample preparations were achieved with methanol and acetonitrile as diluent. The mobile phase was screened based on system suitability (143).

Preparation of buffer solution:

By dissolving 1.26 gram of ammonium formate and taken in 1 litre of volumetric flask adjusted the volume with HPLC grade water to make 20 mM buffer solution and adjusted the final pH to 3.5 by using formic acid. This buffer solution was filtered through the membrane filter of 0.45 μ m porosity and degassed the mobile phase with the help of sonicator (144).

Preparation of Standard Solution:

The primary standard stock solution was prepared by adding 10 mg Remogliflozin and 50 mg Metformin in to 80 ml of diluent and then make the final volume of volumetric flask up to the 100 ml with the same diluent, sonicated for 10 min with the help of sonicator for complete dissolve the drugs and after sonication, volume makes up 100 ml with the same solvent. Take the volume of primary standard stock solution (0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.25, 1.5, and 2.5) make up to 10 ml with the same diluent. The final concentration of Remogliflozin and Metformin was found to be 2.5 to 25 μ g ml⁻¹ and 12.5 to 125 μ g ml⁻¹, respectively for linearity and other analytical methods. The final solution was filtered through a 0.45 μ m Millipore membrane filter.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

20 tablets of different brands of Remogliflozin and Metformin were accurately weighed and then crushed to form the powder equivalent to 10 mg Remogliflozin and Metformin 50 mg which was then transferred into a cleaned and dried 100 ml volumetric flask. The powder was dissolved into the mobile phase using sonication, made up the volume up to 100 ml with the same solvent and filtered with using a Millipore membrane filter resulting in the

concentrations 10 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. The working sample was repeatedly injected with 20 μl solution by using the flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . The optimum wavelength for detection was set at 243 nm.

Estimation of Remogliflozin and Metformin by RP-HPLC Method:

This study's main objective is to develop and validate a simple, precise, reliable, rapid, more accurate, and least time-consuming High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) method for simultaneous

Remogliflozin and Metformin in API as well as in various formulations comply with ICH guideline. The process was optimized and validated by changing multiple parameters like mobile phase composition, pH, elution technique, flow rate, and appropriate columns to achieve sharp peaks, maximum theoretical plates, less tailing factor, and short analysis time. A typical chromatogram found by the same condition mentioned above is illustrated in Figure.

Figure: Typical Chromatogram of Remogliflozin and Metformin

System suitability:

The system suitability test is essential in validating analytical techniques and confirmation of resolution amongst numerous peaks of interest. All perilous parameters (theoretical plates, retention time, and tailing factor) in the study met complete acceptance every time. % RSD for peak area of six replicate was

found to be 1.01 and 0.88 for Remogliflozin and Metformin, respectively. % RSD for retention time was found to be 1.36 and 0.63 for Remogliflozin and Metformin. The tailing factor was less than 2, and a theoretical plate of greater than 2000 indicates that the technique was satisfied given the conditions.

System suitability of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Injection Number	Retention Time Remogliflozin	Peak Area of Remogliflozin	Retention Time Metformin	Peak Area of Metformin
1	3.164	353872	4.956	1593926
2	3.178	352635	4.888	1587382
3	3.084	347327	4.894	1613925
4	3.146	347328	4.934	1583926
5	3.156	354754	4.952	1618395
6	3.214	354737	4.954	1603936
Mean	3.157	351775.50	4.930	1600248.33
SD ($\pm$)	0.043	3531.16	0.031	14155.45
%RSD	1.36	1.01	0.63	0.88
USP Tailing Factor	1.28		0.95	
USP Plate Count	5245		6547	

System suitability Chromatogram of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Method Validation:

Specificity:

Good resolution and no interference from blank and excipients were observed that this method is specific for simultaneous analyzing of Remogliflozin and Metformin. The explanatory chromatogram did not show any other peak confirming the specificity of this method.

Fig: Sample Chromatogram of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Accuracy

Then recovery was estimated at 80 %, 100 % and 120 % of the selected concentrations. Remogliflozin and Metformin recovery values were determined to be 99.93-100.76 percent and 100.11 to 100.40 percent, respectively, as stated in Table.

Table: Accuracy of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Name of the drug	Spiked amount	Amount of drug (Tablet) μg	Amount of drug (Standard) μg	Total Drug (μg)	Total Found (μg) Mean $\pm$ SD	%R SD	% Recovery
Remogliflozin	80%	5	4	9	9.132 $\pm$ 0.107	1.17	101.47
	100%	5	5	10	9.996 $\pm$ 0.190	1.90	99.96
	120%	5	6	11	11.08 $\pm$ 0.103	0.93	100.76
Metformin	80%	25	20	45	45.05 $\pm$ 0.161	0.36	100.11
	100%	25	25	50	50.20 $\pm$ 0.152	0.30	100.40
	120%	25	30	55	55.10 $\pm$ 0.214	0.39	100.18

Precision:

For the precision study, the overall % RSD of system method precision was found to less than 2, which indicates that the precision achieved successfully within the limit. The results of system precision and method precision are given in Table

Table: System and method precision of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Injection Number	System Precision		Method Precision	
	Peak areas of Remogliflozin	Peak areas of Metformin	% Assay of Remogliflozin	% Assay of Metformin
1	354742	1599372	99.23	99.98
2	351832	1587283	100.45	99.27
3	347281	1586237	100.34	99.45
4	346261	1578289	101.02	101.4
5	356271	1595360	99.99	99.56
6	342637	1573724	101.23	101.59
Mean	349837	1586711	100.37	100.21
SD (±)	5302.76	9749.36	0.72	1.03
RSD (%)	1.56	0.61	0.72	1.02
Acceptance criteria	% RSD value should be ≤ 2			

Robustness:

The robustness of the analytical procedure was established & developed by changing flowrate, pH, wavelength, and mobile phase composition. The robustness data of both drugs have been incorporated in Table

Robustness of Remogliflozin and Metformin:

Condition		Remogliflozin			Metformin		
		% RSD	Tailing Factor	% Recovery	% RSD	Tailing Factor	% Recovery
Change in Flow rate	Normal Condition (1.0ml per minute)	0.56	1.03	100.12	0.17	1.01	99.89
	Flow rate (0.8ml per minute)	0.67	1.11	99.23	0.34	1.23	99.45
	Flow rate (1.2ml per minute)	0.91	1.34	99.11	0.45	1.09	100.45
Change in pH	Normal Condition (3.5)	0.08	1.02	99.78	0.28	1.11	99.78
	pH (3.0)	0.78	1.23	100.11	0.56	1.23	99.29
	pH (4.0)	0.69	1.45	99.66	0.48	1.18	98.99
Change in Wavelength	Normal: Wave Length 243nm	0.08	1.03	99.46	0.89	1.11	99.11
	Wave Length 245nm	0.56	1.34	100.78	0.58	1.09	99.78

	Wave Length 241nm	0.67	1.21	99.23	0.99	1.24	99.45
Change composition of mobile phase	Normal Condition (ACN: Buffer) (40:60)	0.46	1.02	99.34	0.19	1.08	101.23
	(ACN: Buffer) (30:70)	0.98	1.35	101.44	0.89	1.09	100.79
	(ACN: Buffer) (50:50)	0.88	1.04	99.44	0.56	1.21	100.76

Detection and quantitation limits:

The limit of detection and limit of quantitation were found to be 0.42, 1.28 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Remogliflozin and 1.97, 5.96 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Metformin, respectively.

Solution Stability:

The assay analysis was used to test the consistency of the solutions at room temperature at regular intervals. From the beginning to the end, the solution was checked every 2 hours. For active ingredients, Remogliflozin and Metformin, the percent of recovery was between 98.6 and 103.2 percent, and the RSD was less than 2.0 percent, suggesting that the sample and standard solutions were stable for 24 hours.

Assay of tablets:

Percentage purity of three different brands of Remogliflozin and Metformin tablets were calculated by using simultaneous quantification. The mean contents of the formulation are between the acceptable range of 90 to 110 % of the label amount. The results show (Table) indicates that the new method is accurate and precise for quantification of fixed-dose combination of Remogliflozin and Metformin by HPLC technique.

Table Assay of Remogliflozin and Metformin

Marketed Formulation		*Retention Time (min)	*Peak Area	*% Assay
Zucator M	Remogliflozin 100 mg	3.34	348576	99.09
	Metformin 500 mg	5.10	1598328	99.88
Remo M	Remogliflozin 100 mg	3.37	352739	100.27
	Metformin 500 mg	5.12	1608246	100.5
Reniva M	Remogliflozin 100 mg	3.27	357272	101.56
	Metformin 500 mg	4.98	1619353	101.19

Fig: Assay Chromatogram of Tablet

CONCLUSION:

Hence, we can conclude that the developed RP-HPLC method is simple and rapid as it separates components with good chromatographic criteria. Method has short run time and all degradants are well separated from drug. The method was successfully validated for all the validation parameters as per ICH guidelines. The method is stability-indicating and can be used to assess the stability of Remogliflozin Etabonate and metformin hcl in the API and tablet dosage form. The method can be conveniently used for assay of Remogliflozin Etabonate and metformin hcl in API and tablet dosage form.

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